

Receptive field surround stimulation modulates responses of neurons in visual area 21a of the cat

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Introduction

The response of neurons in the primary visual cortex (area 17) to stimuli in the classical receptive field (CRF) may be suppressed by simultaneous stimuli in the area around the CRF (1, 2, 3), particularly when the surround stimulus is of the same orientation as the CRF stimulus (4). Area 21a, an extrastriate region of cortex, receives its principal input from area 17; however, it is not known if neurons in area 21a are susceptible to surround effects like those reported for area 17. We have investigated the effects of stimuli in the receptive field surround on the response of area 21a neurons to an optimised stimulus positioned within the neuron's CRF.

Figure 1: Dorsolateral view showing area 21a (red) in relation to other visual regions of the cat brain

Methods

Experimental subjects were adult cats aged 5-12 months, anaesthetised and cannulated in the femoral artery, femoral vein and trachea. Anaesthesia was induced by ketamine/xylazine (15 mg.kg⁻¹ / 1 mg.kg⁻¹ im) and maintained with an infusion of alfaxalone (Alfaxan, 6 mg.kg⁻¹ iv). Animals were administered atropine sulphate (0.2 mg.kg⁻¹ sc) to reduce respiratory secretion and dexamethasone (1.5 mg.kg⁻¹ im) to reduce cerebral oedema. Pupils were dilated using topical atropine sulphate (mg.ml⁻¹) and nictitating membranes were retracted using topical phenylephrine hydrochloride (2.5 mg.ml⁻¹). Eyes were protected using zero-power contact lenses. During recording animals were paralysed using an infusion of gallamine triethiodide (5 mg.kg⁻¹ h⁻¹) and ventilated with 70% N₂O / 30% O₂; expired CO₂ was maintained near 5% and body temperature at 37°C; blood pressure and heart rate were monitored to ensure adequate anaesthesia. All procedures were carried out in accordance with National Health and Medical Research Council guidelines for animal experimentation, and approved by the UNSW Animal Ethics Committee.

For each isolated cell, drifting sinusoidal grating stimuli were generated using custom software (VisSpike 6.0) developed at the University of New South Wales and presented on cathode ray tube monitors (NEC P1250+, 57cm distance, 640x480, 60Hz, 10cd.m⁻²) to the dominant eye for each cell. The values of spatial and temporal frequency and stimulus orientation were separately optimised. In order to ensure that the surround area was not directly stimulating the cell's classical receptive field (or "patch"), the surround region was then filled with a stimulus using the same parameters while the central receptive field was filled with 50% grey; the diameter of the central patch was then expanded until the cell's response was not distinguishable from background activity.

With patch parameters set, the surrounding region (full-screen, 30x40°) was filled with a stimulus of the same spatial and temporal frequency, differing either in orientation or spatial phase from the central patch. The orientation or phase was then varied in the range 0 to 360°, presented in pseudorandom order. Stimuli were presented five times while the discriminated spikes from the cell were counted. Analysis of the effects of the surround were based on the mean response rate measured across all five presentations.

Figure 3: Degrees of suppression observed in individual cells of area 21a: fourteen cells (red lines) showed reduced responses (patch alone = 1.0) when a grating was presented in the area surrounding the CRF, for all orientations. Six cells showed slight increases (green) or a mixture of increases and reductions (brown); overall these cells' responses were unaffected by stimuli in the surround region.

Figure 2: Response histograms from three single area 21a neurons to each of the grating stimulus conditions. In each case the stimulus parameters were optimised for the neuron under study. The stimulus condition is indicated to the left of the PSTH's, with arrowheads indicating the direction of drift of the grating in the circular patch and in the surround. Double arrowheads in the orthogonal condition indicate that the responses used for analysis were averaged across the two orthogonal directions to eliminate bias.

Figure 4: Mean response rates of neurons (±SEM, n=14) that displayed a reduced response to a grating surrounding the CRF. The response to the patch alone differed significantly from the responses when a grating was presented simultaneously in the surround (p<0.05, ANOVA); the mean responses in each of the surround conditions did not differ significantly from each other.

Results

We recorded activity from 20 single area 21a neurons in response to a grating patch alone, or with the grating patch surrounded by an iso-oriented grating drifting in the same direction, a cross-oriented grating or an iso-oriented grating drifting in the opposite direction. The response to the grating patch was reduced in 14 neurons (70%) when a grating was simultaneously presented in the surround. The difference in response between the patch alone and the patch with a surround stimulus was statistically significant, regardless of the orientation or drift direction of a grating in the surround (p<0.05; ANOVA). Among the cells which did not exhibit surround suppression (n=6), presenting gratings moving in any direction in the surround had no significant effect (p>0.05; ANOVA) on the cell's response; i.e. as a group, these cells were not excited by stimuli in the surround.

Conclusions

The response of most neurons in area 21a to stimulation of the CRF with a grating patch is suppressed by the simultaneous presentation of a grating surrounding the CRF, similar to many neurons in area 17 (1-4). However, the extent of response suppression in area 21a is independent of the orientation and direction of movement of the surround stimulus, which is not the case for neurons in area 17. This suggests that the surround suppression apparent in area 21a neurons is due to local interactions rather than simply reflecting the surround suppression in area 17.

References

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